

Year 1

Year 2

Year 3

Year 4

Year 5

Database of relevant European data for upscaling

Hofman et al.

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1 Introduction

Within the Toolbox (see Milestone 7) and within the goals of WP5 of the SPRINT project, it is planned to **estimate the inputs (emissions) into the European environment for the active substances (a.s.) of Plant Protection Products (PPP)**. For this, specific PPP data will be needed (see below). Consequently, updated environmental fate models will be used to **predict the environmental distribution** (soil-water-air) of the substances (including the formation and fate of the transformation products). This will be performed mainly in Tools III.B and III.C of the Toolbox (see Milestone 7). The modelled concentrations in the various environmental compartments will be used for the **exposure assessment** and the exposure outputs will be compared with the hazard data to **characterize and map the risk for ecosystems, animals, and humans**. Such outputs will be in Tools IV.A, B, C, and D. With respect to animals and humans, environmental exposure will be complemented by **dietary exposure** assessment using additional data on feed and food from existing databases. In the end, all the impacts and risks predicted as described above will be **integrated into one/global health impact assessment**. This is Tool V.

The pesticide monitoring data from the SPRINT case studies and will be used for the **verification of the predictions** (reality check) together with the other monitoring data from the literature.

The abovementioned estimations/predictions will be performed at **various spatial and temporal scales/levels**:

1. **Country level.** Primarily in the *data-rich countries* having very good spatial (high resolution) and temporal (different years) data on crops and pesticide use, as well as detailed databases of PPP registration data. Then, the concept will be applied also to *representative countries from the southern and northern zones*, where different PPP portfolios, crop portfolios and application patterns might be expected. The data on PPP residues in food are available at comparable quality in most European countries, so these will be started in parallel.
2. **European level.** This will be based both on the summation of the regional and national predictions (bottom-up approach) and the global emission model (top-down approach).

At each level, the uncertainty of the predictions will be carefully indicated or discussed.

1.1 Major data used for the Toolbox estimations/predictions

For all the following activities, general EU list¹ of the approved and non-approved a.s. will be needed as well as the most comprehensive database of pesticides properties².

For the successful **predictions of the pesticide emissions** (i.e., input to the environment), the following data inputs will be mainly needed:

- **PPP registers** – national data on registered PPP; in particular, application patterns (quantity, frequency, and time of the crop-specific applications), PPP properties (composition, a.s. concentration), etc.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/active-substances/?event=search.as>

² <http://sitem.herts.ac.uk/aeru/ppdb/en/index.htm>

- **PPP usage** – national statistics on pesticides; consumption of each a.s. per specific period in the specific area and for the specific crop
- **crop data** - maps with sufficient spatial and temporal resolution; phenology data that will enable to link relative time data of PPP applications (at BBCH scale) with real calendar times

More about data from **PPP registers** and data on the **PPP usage** is described in [Chapter 2](#).

For the **crop data**, we have validated the novel pan-European crop map using the Dutch national data based on real farmers' reports. The results are shown in [Chapter 3](#).

For **dietary exposure**, the following data will be needed:

- **PPP residues in food** – annual reports from individual countries reporting a.s. residues in different food types
- **food consumption patterns** – food basket for each country and daily consumption of commodities

We have started to compile these data in the individual European countries. This work is described in [Chapter 4](#).

The work related to **the global emission model** for the pan-European predictions is more clarified in [Chapter 5](#).

2 Pesticide usage and PPP data

2.1 Introduction

In the European Union, there is a robust legislative framework to ensure the sustainable and safe PPP use. This can be promoted with suitable instruments available. For instance, PPP related data of sufficient quality, validity and resolution are needed for the implementation of this framework. The EU Member States (EU MSs) are collecting relevant registration data for the PPP that are placed into the market and are used in the agricultural land of their territories in alignment with Regulation 1107/2009³ and other relevant legislation. EU MSs are also obliged to report usage of pesticides according to Regulation 1185/2009⁴. European countries that are not members of the EU also may retain registers of authorized PPP and their uses under the responsibility of competent national authorities. Such datasets hold a great potential to achieve common agricultural policy goals, however, it is vague whether they are of **sufficient level of harmonization, quality, and quantity** to be utilized towards sustainable agriculture aims.

This chapter describes:

- i) the state of the PPP registers
- ii) the source of PPP uses recorded across the European countries

The two main sources searched for this aim are the EPPPO region database for the PPP registers⁵, and the database of Eurostat on the pesticide use in agriculture for the PPP usage⁶. The links, institutional contacts, the data types, and data evaluations provided openly in these database sources were investigated based on standardized criteria and extent (see next sub-chapters).

It should be noted that this investigation was conducted by RECETOX MU (Masaryk University), using the PPP database retained by the competent authority of the Czech Republic (The Central Institute for Supervising and Testing in Agriculture - CISTA) as a **reference model**. The example of the Czech database is in detail described next. An **operational PPP database system** was constructed at RECETOX MU providing opportunities for utilizing data-rich collection for the research aims of the SPRINT project. Below, an example of such output and the information power it may provide are demonstrated.

To upscale relevant data from local to regional levels up to the global, it is of high importance to firstly percolate in the properties of these data systems of each country and seep into parameters or properties underneath three main criteria, i.e., **availability, accessibility, and data resolution**. This chapter entails an appraisal of data on PPPs collected across countries of Europe based on these three main criteria. It is underlined, that **this appraisal does not constitute criticism** of the ways, means, and resources the national authorities allocate and use to maintain their national data systems of registered PPPs and their uses. It is a **review of our current capability to gather relevant data for utilizing them across scales from local to global**. As such, the outcome this chapter provides is our **up-to-date knowledge and understanding of the PPP databases' (PPP registers and use statistics) status and properties of the European countries**. Thus, the output presented in this chapter is

³ Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market

⁴ Regulation (EC) No 1185/2009 concerning statistics on pesticides

⁵ The EPPPO databases of registered PPPs:

https://www.eppo.int/ACTIVITIES/plant_protection_products/registered_products

⁶ The Eurostat sources: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/aei_pestuse_esms.htm

subject to amendments over time as the depth of our investigation will progress stepwise from this standardized initial search to more thorough understanding of the data retained in each country.

Overall, **39 countries** of the European territory were checked for the above topics (see [Table 2.1](#)). Transcontinental countries and countries under special territory (e.g., de facto, or dependent) and sovereignty states were not included in the list or investigation. Andorra, Liechtenstein, Monaco, San Marino, and Holy See (the Vatican City) were also excluded, as it was not currently possible to derive online relevant agricultural indicators for these states. The list of 39 countries entails the 27 states that are currently Members of the European Union (EU MSs), and the results for the EU MSs are also presented separately. The EU regulatory zones the formulated PPPs are authorized were also considered.

The EPPO and Eurostat sources (see above) were checked thoroughly for each country. **A contact template** was compiled based on the quality and resolution of the Czech PPP database system available at RECETOX MU. This template was modified with specific questions, if needed, for each country according to our findings in their open links and sources available. It should be noted that comparison with the Czech datasets is not fit-for-purpose at this stage as the depth of the current search for the rest countries is different from the one implemented for the Czech Republic, and therefore the level of data quality and resolution cannot be comparable.

For the **PPP register** of each country, we have asked if there is available, accessible, and resolute data on:

- the list of formulated products authorized in the country*
- the a.s. content in the formulated product (guaranteed composition)*
- the application rates and crops the product is applied (with crop-names available with EPPO codes)*
- the way of application*
- the intervals between applications, the times of application, the BBCH stage of application*
- the type of pesticide (mode of action)*
- the approval decision*
- the authorization holders*
- the decision owner*
- the units of application (e.g., kg/ha)*
- the pests that are targeted (with pest names available with EPPO codes)*
- the date the decision of approval and trading is valid (e.g., from xxx until xxx)*
- the date of the end of trading*
- the date of the end of approval*
- pre-harvest intervals*
- buffer zones and/or drift-reduction*

For the **pesticide usage** of each country, we considered the Eurostat Handbook of Annual crop statistics, 2020 Edition⁷, which was recommended to be applied by the European countries. Then, we checked the Eurostat assessments for each country. Hence, we contacted the countries and asked for data available for the amounts of a.s. used in an agricultural area (i.e., hectareage, kg a.s./ha) for the district areas of the country and for crop types. In addition, it was asked whether such data are directly retrieved (as original) from surveys on actual PPP amounts used for the utilized agricultural land of the country in

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/749240/7023703/CROP-ESS-2015-25-15-amended-by-ESS-2020-42-6-Annual-crop-statistics.pdf/1c6a527d-1d27-c20f-4e0f-284e262da75c>

total, and for different districts and crop types and if such resolute data can be openly retrieved or provided by institutions for research aims.

It is pinpointed here that with some countries there has been continuous contact while with some others there is currently difficulty in reaching basic links or contacts, or this communication process is still in progress. As it is shown in the next sections, **the outcome for either PPP registers or PPP use repositories is quite variable, dependent on, but not currently clear if also analogous to, our own to-date capability to reach the suitable and eligible staff contact and acquire the relevant information.**

However, it calls, at this stage already, for a cross-boundary, cross-institutional harmonized system, or common platform of such repositories, with common criteria of resolute data collection if such data are to be utilized for research and monitoring of PPPs amounts in the European environment.

Table 2.1. List of countries for which the PPP registers and usage were investigated. Marking with an x indicates sources and data availability (that we were able to reach so far) irrespective of the level of accessibility, resolution, and the differences (data comparability) among the countries and across institutes or sources. Asterisk indicates the country is an EU Member State. The received feedback is presented in the next sections of this chapter. The basic sources that were used: the EPPO region database for the PPP registers⁸, and the database of Eurostat on the pesticide use in agriculture for the PPP usage⁹. Transcontinental countries and countries under special territory (e.g., de facto, or dependent) and sovereignty states were not included in the list or investigation. Andorra, Liechtenstein, Monaco, San Marino, and Holy See (the Vatican City) were also excluded, as it was not possible to derive online agricultural indicators for these states.

Nr	Country	Code	PPP register	PPP usage
1	Albania	AL		
2	Austria *	AT	x	x
3	Belarus	BY	x	
4	Belgium *	BE	x	x
5	Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA		
6	Bulgaria *	BG	x	x
7	Croatia *	HR	x	x
8	Cyprus *	CY	x	x
9	Czech Republic (Czechia) *	CZ	x	x
10	Denmark *	DK	x	x
11	Estonia *	EE	x	x
12	Finland *	FI	x	x
13	France *	FR	x	x
14	Germany *	DE	x	x
15	Greece (Hellas) *	GR	x	x
16	Hungary *	HU	x	x
17	Iceland	IS		
18	Ireland *	IE	x	x
19	Italy *	IT	x	x
20	Latvia *	LV	x	x
21	Lithuania	LT	x	x

⁸ The EPPO databases of registered PPPs:

https://www.eppo.int/ACTIVITIES/plant_protection_products/registered_products

⁹ The Eurostat sources: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/aei_pestuse_esms.htm

22	Luxembourg *	LU	x	x
23	Malta *	MT	x	x
24	Moldova	MD	x	
25	Montenegro	ME		
26	Netherlands *	NL	x	x
27	North Macedonia	MK		
28	Norway *	NO	x	x
29	Poland *	PL	x	x
30	Portugal *	PT	x	x
31	Romania *	RO	x	x
32	Serbia	RS	x	
33	Slovakia *	SK	x	x
34	Slovenia *	SI	x	x
35	Spain *	ES	x	x
36	Sweden *	SE	x	x
37	Switzerland	CH	x	
38	Ukraine	UA		
39	United Kingdom	UK	x	x

2.2 Overview of metadata investigation per country

We have prepared a detailed overview of the investigation per country for all the countries listed in **Table 2.1**. Below, the **selected examples** are presented that **depict variability across countries** and the importance of assigning quality criteria when the statuses of national PPP registers are investigated.

Czech Republic – reference model of PPP database (PPP register and use) used in a country

This is the most detailed database of such data compiled for SPRINT so far and the most advanced database set up for the following analyses and predictions.

For the PPP register, there is available an online search in the Czech language with very high resolution (each approved decision is available together with huge specific data). For the PPP use, there are PDF tables published for each year containing the annual use of each a.s. for the selected crops. Despite this, the competent authorities (UZKUZ & Czech Ministry of Agriculture) were contacted regularly and systematically to achieve access of all these data in useful format and resolution.

PPP register data were provided in XML format containing the full PPP register and daily updates. This was imported into the PostgreSQL database system – as a PPP data warehouse in cooperation with RECETOX Data Services Infrastructure. Then, using the SQL programming language e.g., in the DBeaver software (<https://dbeaver.io>), these data can be mined using specific SQL commands and scripts.

As was explained above, for the PPP register of the CR, there are resolute data on: *the list of formulated products authorized in the country, the a.s. content in the formulated product (guaranteed composition), the minimum and maximum application rates and the crops the product is applied (with crop-names available with EPPO codes), the way of application, the intervals between applications, the times of*

application, the BBCH stage of application, the type of pesticide (mode of action), the approval decision, the authorization holders, the decision owners, the units (e.g., kg/ha), the pests that are targeted (with pest-names available with EPPO codes), the date the decision of approval and trading is valid (e.g. from xxx until xxx), the date of the end of trading, the date of the end of approval, pre-harvest intervals, buffer zones and/or drift-reduction.

For the PPP usage in the CR, there are data available for the amount of PPP a.s. used in an agricultural area (i.e., hectare, kg a.s./ha) for the district areas of the Czech territory and for crop types cultivated in the country. Information on the method of PPP usage estimates is available.

The Czech database is the outcome of the deepest level of search that was achieved so far for collecting relevant data set up to be analysed. The database is currently being revised with even more resolute and updated data, and where needed, with English terms. The database entails more than 40,000 entries corresponding to diverse types of decision approvals per PPP, for all the years the repository is retained by the national authorities.

Finland – Example of a country with resolute data to a specific extent, with old PPP register retained, potentially accessible, though in several ways from various sources and limitations

KEMIDIGI is currently the official register and is updated regularly. PPPs with an active registration post 06/2011 were migrated from the old PPP-register to KEMIDIGI in 2020-2021. All the regulatory history (excluding documents and no-longer relevant data fields) related to this PPP-subset was migrated, though the new system contains quite a lot of structured fields that were not available in the old registry. Data related to older PPPs (i.e., not approved since 06/2011), is currently being archived. Data in KEMIDIGI are published also in .json format. There is an available online database with code/value groups used in it.

PPPs, Biocides and Chemical Products share a common 'Substance registry' in KEMIDIGI, which is sourced from ECHAs database and supplemented with additional data/substances. For PPPs, some additional data is provided regarding FRAC (Fungicide Resistance Action Committee), HRAC (Herbicide Resistance Action Committee) and IRAC (Insecticide Resistance Action Committee) MoA (Mode of Action) classifications (this is still incomplete) and Eurostat Code, though some of this information may nowadays be available also in ECHAs database.

At the website of TUKES, clearly some of the data is readily available (Products, authorization periods, compositions) and some of it requires extensive labour (Application related information). There are some limits on what the institute can do and, depending on the nature of the work, the general fees of TUKES may be applied.

On the amounts of PPPs used in the Finnish agricultural land, TUKES is responsible for collecting the sales data. The product sales data is directly linked to the authorisation holder and a case where access to it has been granted, is rather not existing, but this is something that needs to be verified. The a.s. level data can be only indirectly linked to the authorisation holders in some cases, making it confidential, but access to the data can be granted for research purposes.

Additional sources can be found from pesticide retailers that have put more effort in structuring the GAP-data and a request of the data they have available could be possible. LUKE is responsible for the pesticide use statistics.

The Finnish Environmental Institute has done some estimation of application rates across Finland and can be found online.

TUKES was contacted for the above issues and discussions for data resolution are currently in progress.

France – example of a country with highly resolute data up to interactive maps, but language limitation

In the EPPO databases of registered PPPs the websites can be searched of: *e-PHY database (ANSES) + e-PHY files Open Data; AGRITOX (maintained by ANSES - physical and chemical properties, toxicology and ecotoxicology of a.s. registered in France); UIPP (French Crop Protection Association - datasheets on safety aspects of commercial products)*

At e-PHY database (ANSES) + e-PHY files Open Data, there is the possibility to search by substance (but one-by-one alphabetically). But not any option is obvious to download the PPP register, e.g., as an excel file, either for products or for a.s.. ANSES was contacted to request further assistance in retrieving data, and it was clarified that open databases are available. These have open data from the e-PHY catalogue of PPP, fertilisers and growing media, adjuvants, combination products and mixtures, and information on PPP marketing authorisations of up to 120 days issued by the Ministry in phytosanitary emergency situations.

For the PPP amounts used in the European agricultural land, according to the Eurostat sources, there are maps and data available online (AGRESTE). There is information (also in graphs) on agricultural holdings and the areas that are used as cultivated land (divided into three categories) and no detail on crop types. Also, while the resolution is amazingly great from local to district to country level, rather it is not possible to find data on the amount of PPP a.s. that are really used per hectare in each different district or category of agricultural holding. The maps of agricultural indicators are interactive.

The National Agency for Health, Food, Environmental and Occupational Safety (ANSES) was contacted for the above issues.

Germany – example of a country with resolute relevant data and payment requirement

For the PPP register of Germany, in the EPPO databases of registered PPPs two links of BVL (Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety) are available in German. There is the possibility to retrieve data by searching the PPP one by one, or by using filters.

At the website of BVL on information on authorized PPPs, the PPP register, a free-of-charge Online database and a concise list are available. The PPP register contains the authorized products with comprehensive information on classification and labelling, use restrictions, and directions for use. The register is published annually and is available as print and pdf download. The free-of-charge internet database allows for searches for the authorized PPPs. The data are updated in monthly intervals. Quarterly, the BVL issues a concise bilingual (German / English) list of authorized PPPs. Included is a list of terminated authorizations. The above information can be downloaded as excel and pdf files.

The free-of-charge Online database on PPP provides search option directly or stepwise. English instructions on how to use the database are available online and can be downloaded as pdf file. Also, codes and text of all labelling requirements, directions for use and permitted information phrases are

compiled in a separate file. Prints of the register in its previous format can be ordered from Saphir Verlag with payment.

The information on authorized PPPs is available also as a database file. The file is updated monthly and currently has the format MS-Access 2000. It contains the same information which appears in the online database and the PPP register. Governmental authorities have free access to the file for their legal duties. For other users, there is a subscription price per year or for a month. Contact for information and orders is available online.

UBA (Federal Environment Agency), the Federal Portal (bund.de, Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community (BMI) and BVL were contacted for all the above issues.

For the PPP amounts used in the agricultural land of the German territory, and according to the Eurostat metadata sources, data are published regularly at the website of Julius Kuehn Institute (JKI). There are only crop-specific overviews at irregular intervals. On the website are displayed findings, and surveys can be downloaded as pdf reports in German. The data collection on PPP use started in 2001. Yearly surveys are conducted since 2011. The responsible institute is the Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants (JKI), Institute for Strategies and Technology Assessment. Contacts are available for data requests.

Italy – example of a country with variable data split across different sources and variable accessibility conditions and resolution

One link of the Italian Ministry of Health is available listing registered PPPs. There is the possibility to search by product name (but one-by one in Italian). There is also the option to download the data, as an excel file, but useful resolute information is missing. For instance, the application regimes, the crops each formulated product is applied, the products that are approved for each active substance, the decisions of approval that entail such information or others, like the buffer zones. Therefore, the PPP sector of the Italian Ministry of Environment (MiTE) was contacted to investigate if there is any other source of information. It was clarified that some information is available on the website of the Italian Ministry of Health. This information is however limited.

In addition, there is the MiTE inventory "Sistema Informativo utilizzo FitoSanitari" from a project. Information from EFSA (European Food Safety Authority) conclusions that can be found publicly in the EFSA journal, is collected, and organized in a concise way, and mostly for (eco)toxicity endpoints and results. The MiTE inventory is very helpful because it compares different pesticide a.s. by assigning scores (low, medium, high) to specific properties (e.g., toxicity).

In addition, the ICPS (International Centre for Pesticides and Health Risk Prevention) of Italy was contacted and it was clarified that in ICPS, there is information like the list of formulated products authorized in Italy or the a.s. content in the formulated product (guaranteed composition) or the functional class. However, these data are not organized in a single database. As for application rates, intervals between applications, the times of application, the BBCH stage of application, the units (e.g., kg/ha), the pests that are targeted, the pre-harvest intervals and buffer zones, this information has to be extracted from the pesticide labels. It was therefore suggested to check the public PESTIDOC online database and the FITOGEST private project. These tasks are currently in progress.

For the PPP amounts used in the European agricultural land, according to the Eurostat sources there are survey reports online at the ISTAT - Italian National Institute of Statistics. However, there are no data according to individual a.s..

It should be noted that there is the report of JRC (Joint Research Center of the European Commission) and ICPS on "Estimating pesticide use across the EU" ¹⁰. This work is considered among the 'example tools' for SPRINT. The ICPS was contacted, and it was clarified that regarding Italy, information was retrieved from the SIAN database, but it is not available anymore and the pesticide data were available only for 2012. Data were aggregated to Italian Regions, and there were percentages of pesticide classes at Provincial level, so that potential crop application (obtained from PPP labels) could be used with pesticide classes and crop coverage from ISTAT to redistribute the amount of pesticide sold in 2012 over Provinces (NUTS3).

Serbia - Example of a country where some metadata are only available aggregated as an official biannual publication

There is a link suggested in the EPPO database of registered Plant Protection Products: Вести - Управа за заштиту биља from the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management - Plant Protection Directorate. This link provides a pdf file listing the approved PPPs in Serbia. It was not possible to find online more resolute data about the registered PPPs in Serbia or an English version.

Regarding the approved a.s., Serbian legislation is harmonized with EU, and the link to the page of approved a.s. is on the website of "Uprava za zastitu bilja". Regarding the products, rather not any information for resolute data can be found at the Government website. There is a book named "Pesticidi u prometu" (Pesticides on the market in Serbia), that is published every two years, and it covers all the formulated products registered for use with information as content: protected plant, pathogen/pest organism, application rate, etc. The last publication was two years ago, and soon the new edition will be published; however (1) it is in the Serbian language, no English version is available and (2) it is available only in print.

For the PPP amounts used in the Serbian agricultural land, information regarding pesticide use (consumption), and amount imported into the environment, both by regions or the whole country, is not available or rather accessible.

2.3 PPP registers - data availability among countries – state of relevance for upscaling from local to larger areas of Europe

As was referred in the 2.1 Introduction, the main search criteria for the PPP registers of the European countries were: **availability, accessibility, and data resolution**. Accessibility was added as a criterion, distinguished from availability because the fact that there is data deposited in a country is not a prerequisite for easy or adequate access to it. How easy, and if the documents can be retrieved from an online link is a different question that lies more within the criterion of accessibility. Data resolution is a criterion that does not define the quality of data, standalone. Also, it is not meant by the term "data

¹⁰ Galimberti F, Dorati C, Udias A, Pistocchi A. Estimating pesticide use across the EU. Accessible data and gap-filling. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2020. ISBN: 978-92-76-13098-7. 2020.

resolution" that the same level of quality and detail of data can be retrieved, as was done for the database of the Czech Republic, because the followed process, in this case, reached a deeper level of search and was long-term. Therefore, specific properties were assigned to each of the three criteria to explicitly describe them (explanations in parentheses):

Availability:

- online source/link (is there online source/link with any information?)
- "search" option (is there any "search: option in this link?)
- institutional database (is there any evidence that a database is retained?)
- documentation/reporting (are there any documents available apart from the "search option"?)

Accessibility

- contacts (is there contact option or information available online for data retrieval?)
- database open at website (is the database available online?)
- documents open at website documents/data retrieved (can documents or data available be retrieved?)
- easiness of resolute database retrieval (can more resolute data be easily retrieved?)
- no payment requirement (is data provision free of charge?)
- instructions/ operation manual (is there any instructions or operation manual for searching the database or retrieving data online?)
- English version (is there any English version of data available?)

Data resolution

- (Is there resolute information related to...?):
- active substance
- formulated product
- decision approval
- application regime
- crop
- pest

To qualitatively evaluate the status for each property of the above criteria a **scale of four colours** was used and is described in the below key:

Grey: answers difficult to identify through source/link (for instance when no answer can be provided, or no information could be found at the period of searching).

Green: answers "yes" or "sufficient/high" to the question of the property

Yellow: answers "possible" or "partly" or "in progress" to the question of the property

Red: answers "no" or "lacking/low" to the question of the property

In **Table 2.2** the status of the PPP registers is presented for all 39 searched countries. For each property of the three criteria, a colour-score is assigned with the colour-scale described above. For each criterion, an estimate of the total score is provided as "score," to display a general overview of the status of the PPP register data of the country. High variability among the three criteria, and across countries is observed. This depicts the **differences in the ways and structures the countries are collecting and maintaining these data**, and the limitations or obstacles related to accessibility, and resolute data

retrieval. This also entails other implications: for instance, when access to data is possible and easy but **different terms are used for the same variables** is a fact that poses difficulty in comprehending whether sufficient resolute data are available and accessible (e.g., the “mode of action” can be described in the PPP register of another country as “function” or “use” or “category”). Apart from common terminology, the **language is another obstacle** to overcome to meet objectives of upscaling. In many websites there is the option “translate to English” however either it is not functional, or it is not precise or correct.

As it is shown in **Table 2.2** about data availability, most of the countries investigated here possess a PPP register at a source that **links to data available either as aggregated metadata online or as document formats**. It is not always easy to identify from these sources if a regularly updated PPP register is indeed maintained in the respective competent national institution over time. However, in most cases, it appears that there is such PPP register available irrespective of the degree of data resolution, and accessibility. The greatest limitations to be resolved are identified with respect to accessibility and resolution of data. While for several countries detailed data are available, they are stored online in a way that **deprives from direct or easy provision**. It is yet unclear, whether the countries charge fees for resolute data provision, depending also on the level of resolution that is requested. In general, **difficulty is detected in retrieving data of high resolution** following comprehensive instructions in English without fees charged. Regarding resolute data, the current overview shows that data on application regimes, crop and pest targeted are reported with much less detail. While it is more common that decision identification or protocol numbers, summaries and data related to formulated product (trading, content, approval periods and owners) are most often reposit with higher detail and precision.

When considering only the **overall scores for the three criteria** (**Table 2.2** – summary), another aspect is revealed. Data-rich PPP registers of high resolution cannot be easily provided unless **each entry of many thousands is retrieved separately** (one-by-one), a process that would be time and human-resource consuming, depriving of possibilities to utilize such datasets for upscaling, although comparability with the resolute data of the Czech Republic would be highly possible (e.g., Greece). In other cases, the links and the databases are old and therefore the search options are obsolete and rather **not comprehensive enough for relevant data provision** (e.g., the Belgian old repository is currently under revision). The complexity of detecting all the sources available for deriving resolute relevant data of PPP register is also presented with the yellow-marked properties in **Table 2.2**, indicating that either many contacts are still in progress for clarifications or data are partly available. There are cases that it is investigated whether more data can be derived (e.g., for Italy different pieces of information are split across different institutes or the private sector), a fact that adds more complexity to the already existing limitations reported above. An important issue that should not be neglected is **the format the (online) documents are available**. Data analysis and manipulation to upscale from local to regional and global levels, means that the format of the data for such large databases is software specific, and this adds another factor of complexity.

When considering the **27 EU MSs** (**Table 2.3**) the overview is similar. The only difference is that due to the general guidance provided in the EPPO and Eurostat databases within the context of EC Regulations the 1107/2009 and 1185/2009, **at least aggregated data can be identified**. In contrast, in several European countries that are not members of the European Union there was practical difficulty in identifying such sources, and if not, the level of harmonization with the EU criteria for data availability differed (e.g., Serbia). Currently, it seems that for some countries due to particularities no data (grey colour) can be found, however this may not be true (e.g., Montenegro, Ukraine).

Table 2.4 (a, b, c) presents the overview for each regulatory EU zone (considering the authorization process of PPPs).

Overall, some countries provide national data on the authorized PPP in **systematic way providing a lot of valuable details for analyses** (e.g., composition of PPP, application rates, target crops and pests, application BBCH). In other countries, these data are **confidential or of very low quality**. The collections and presentation of the authorized PPP data (i.e., national PPP registers) are **considerably variable by means of the quality, resolution, and format** (see the links to national PPP databases of EPPO). This limits interoperability of these data at EU-wide scale. From these reasons, these data are **used only rarely or not at all for policy making and strategic decisions despite their enormous information potential**. Harmonization of the PPP registers, the stored data resolution and the output formats will capitalize in precise reporting of pesticide use and will enable predictions of pesticide loads in variable scenarios. Recent evaluation of Directive for Sustainable Use of Pesticides¹¹ recommended among other issues to develop EU-wide database for the use of different categories of pesticides and their application rates. It is needed to identify the barriers for EU-wide harmonization and transparency of national registers of authorized PPP, set the platform of national and European stakeholders relevant in authorized PPP data collection, analyse European and national legislative set-ups including confidentiality issues and prepare technical solution of the harmonized platform of authorized PPP data.

2.4 Pesticide use data - data availability among countries – state of relevance for upscaling from local to larger areas of Europe

Likewise, the same three criteria were used for assessing the status of **PPP-usage data** in the utilized agricultural lands of the European countries. In this case, **data resolution** is specified according to the properties:

- frequency of data collection (Is data yearly collected?)
- local/ district specific (is data collection district specific?)
- agricultural holding (is agricultural holding the area unit of data collection?)
- actual PPP amount (data collected on actual PPP amount used?)
- a.s. specific (is data collection a.s. specific?).

Note that the same key applies for the **coloured scale** used to qualitatively evaluate the status for each property of availability and accessibility. In addition, for data resolution the key is modified as follows:

Grey: answers difficult to identify through source/link (for instance when no answer can be provided, or no information could be found at the period of searching) or just once reported.

Green: answers “yes” or “sufficient/high” or “yearly” or “agricultural holding” to the question of the property

Yellow: answers “possible” or “partly” or “in progress” or “medium” or “field area different from agricultural holding” to the question of the property

¹¹ <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/our-work/opinions-information-reports/information-reports/evaluation-directive-sustainable-use-pesticides-information-report>

Red: answers “no” or “lacking/low” or “once in 4 or 5-year period” or “sales data” to the question of the property.

In **Table 2.5**, the **respective status of the data on PPP uses** in the agricultural land of the European territory is presented for all 39 searched countries. Even **higher discrepancies across countries regarding data accessibility, and resolution** are observed compared to the PPP registers. An important aspect is the **high level of aggregation in the Eurostat metadata**. Also, the selection of specific year for reporting to Eurostat, while data are available for other seasons or years and reports are not easily accessible or even detected through online sources or contacts. Most countries claim **specific confidentiality restrictions**. Thorough search of the Eurostat data and national websites revealed **inconsistency in the methods of estimating the PPP usage and hectareage**. Several countries use **original data from surveys to farmers** while other countries use **data on sales** and apply **extrapolation** to derive estimates of the amounts that potentially would be used (this is reported by Eurostat as overestimation). **Language and terminology pose limitations** for this kind of data as in the case of the PPP register. For instance, most of the countries define the agricultural holding as the unit used for the usage and hectareage. However, the definition of “agricultural holding” varies across countries in area size (ha) and different terms used, e.g., crop fields or parcels, may mean “agricultural holding”. The low or irregular frequency of data collection, the lack of active-substance specific surveys, and the lack of data collected at local/district levels are significant factors that limit the quality of this type of data. Difficulty in retrieving resolute data is also shown in Table 2.5.

This overview does not differ for the EU MSs data (**Table 2.6**). Across the different regulatory EU zones (**Table 2.7**) it can be noticed that the status of data availability and resolution is rather **more enhanced in the central and north zones** compared to the southern EU zone. It is worth noting that for the countries that are not EU MSs and were not included in the Eurostat lists the degree of difficulty or complexity to access and clarify such data was higher.

In conclusion, the data on pesticide use are currently collected based on Regulation (EC) No 1185/2009 in Eurostat database. They are available for aggregated groups as major groups, categories of products and chemical classes. **Several factors hinder a beneficial use of the data collected** (for example, they cannot be used for calculating risk indicators as initially targeted). The **level of individual a.s.** is not available at the EU level. However, as the hazard and consequently risk is a.s. specific, data on use for individual a.s. are highly needed for PPP related policy making and strategic monitoring. National methodologies for the data collection differs and sometimes are of low quality. The data suffer from the **wide variety in crops and reference periods chosen** by countries. Revision of the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive¹² comments that use and sales data are **not collected in a satisfactory format for policy making**. It emphasizes the **need of effective and coherent gathering of these data** and calls for **mandatory collection and sharing of more detailed statistics on pesticides use**. Also, the European Parliament's report¹³ calls to establish a **fully operational and transparent system for the regular collection of statistical data on pesticide use**. Report of the European Court of Auditors¹⁴ considers the data collected and available as not sufficient to allow effective monitoring of sustainable PPP use and calls for improving statistics on PPPs when revising the legislation to make them more accessible, useful, and comparable. Further harmonization was indicated in the Eurostat Handbook, but Eurostat does not have the power to prescribe EU Member States how the data collection should be carried out in a harmonized way. It is needed to prepare a detailed inventory of national strategies of

¹² <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/our-work/opinions-information-reports/information-reports/evaluation-directive-sustainable-use-pesticides-information-report>

¹³ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-8-2019-0082_EN.html?redirect

¹⁴ https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR20_05/SR_Pesticides_EN.pdf

PPP use data collection, identify the barriers for EU-wide harmonization of the methodology (including confidentiality issues), explore the legislative environment on pesticide statistics and its innovation towards more accessible and comparable data with sufficient resolution (a.s. and district specific), set the platform of national and European stakeholders relevant in PPP use data collection, and prepare technical solution of the harmonized collection of PPP use data.

2.5 Utilization of information when resolute data are available – The example of the Czech Republic

2.5.1 PPP register data

The following **examples of specific queries** show the power of using tools and properly structured resolute databases for deriving scientific output useful to research objectives, management and policy making. The database of the Czech Republic was used for this purpose. For the current examples, the DBeaver software, the PostgreSQL programming language, and the data from the Czech institutes (continuous communication) are used. An example of specific queries is used for an a.s. and the outcome of the scripts when executed is displayed. The Czech database retained at RECETOX MU entails data on PPPs authorizations, a.s., application regimes, uses, pests and crops targeted (**Figure 2.1**) and is organized based on a specific and encoded structure (**Figure 2.2**).

<ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ the list of authorized formulated PPP,✓ the a.s. content in the PPP, product (guar. composition),✓ the type of pesticide (MoA),✓ the application rates with the units (e.g., kg/ha),✓ the application regime (way, intervals, times, crops, pests, BBCH)✓ pre-harvest intervals,	<ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ the approval decision & the decision owners,✓ the authorization holders,✓ the date the decision of approval and trading is valid,✓ the date of the end of trading,✓ the date of the start/end of approval,✓ buffer zones and/or drift-reduction...
--	---

Figure 2.1. PPP Data entailed in the Database system of RECETOX MU for the Czech Republic

Figure 2.2. Dataset structure, codes, and links in the PPP database of the Czech Republic.

A first hypothesis or query is that it is necessary to see all entries and related PPP data for the a.s. metazachlor, then more specific queries can be executed on specific parameters and estimates (e.g., counts of entries). Using the below scripts, we can derive the following outcomes.

Script 1: all data related to metazachlor

```
select *
from
zb_stg_por.stg_active_subs sas,
zb_stg_por.stg_application sa ,
zb_stg_por.stg_decision sd ,
zb_stg_por.stg_decision_as sda ,
zb_stg_por.stg_ppp sp ,
zb_stg_por.stg_use su
where name_en = 'Metazachlor';
```


Outcome 1: A table with all entries of metazachlor (thousands of lines) and related data (columns) is produced:

Script 2: specific parameters (e.g., trade name, maximum and minimum application rates of PPPs, approval decision data) for all PPPs containing metazachlor

```

SELECT
--ppp.trade_name,
--ppp.id,
--deci.reg_number,
deci.id,
deci.package,
asu.name_en,
--asu.id,
das.amount,
das.unit,
sc.crops_name_cz,
sa.min_rate,
sa.max_rate,
sa.unit

--count(*)
from
zb_stg_por.stg_decision deci
left join zb_stg_por.stg_ppp ppp on ppp.id = deci.id_ppp
left join zb_stg_por.stg_decision_as das on deci.id = das.dec_id
left join zb_stg_por.stg_active_subs asu on das.act_substance_id = asu.id
left join zb_stg_por.stg_use su on deci.id = su.decision_id

```



```

left join zb_stg_por.stg_use_crop suc on su.hash = suc.use_hash
left join zb_stg_por.stg_crop sc on suc.crops_hash = sc.hash
left join zb_stg_por.stg_application sa on sa.use_hash = su.hash

```

WHERE

```

name_en LIKE ('%Metazachlor%')
and deci.reg_number NOT LIKE ('%D%') AND deci.reg_number NOT LIKE ('%V%')
--and deci.package not like ('M') and deci.package not like ('V') ???
and (deci.dec_valid_till ::date BETWEEN '2020-01-01' AND '2020-12-31'
or deci.dec_valid_from ::date BETWEEN '2020-01-01' AND '2020-12-31'
or (deci.dec_valid_from ::date < '2020-01-01' AND deci.dec_valid_till ::date > '2020-12-31'))

```

```

--group by
--asu.name_en,
--sc.crops_type

```

```

order by
deci.id;

```

Outcome 2: a table with the requested only parameters is displayed.

deci_id	deci_package	asu_name_en	deci_amount	deci_unit	deci_crops_name_cz	deci_min_rate	deci_max_rate	deci_unit
1	Metazachlor	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
2	27,630	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
3	27,631	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
4	27,696	Metazachlor	200	g/l	Levická seta ošmá			
5	27,696	Metazachlor	200	g/l	Levická seta jarní			
6	28,546	Metazachlor	333	g/l				
7	28,549	Metazachlor	333	g/l				
8	28,600	Metazachlor	333	g/l	Levická seta jarní			
9	28,600	Metazachlor	333	g/l	Levická seta ošmá			
10	28,635	Metazachlor	375	g/l				
11	29,302	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
12	29,325	Metazachlor	333	g/l	Holčice samptská			
13	29,325	Metazachlor	333	g/l	Řepka ošmá			
14	29,325	Metazachlor	333	g/l	Řepka jarní			
15	29,644	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
16	29,819	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
17	30,271	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
18	30,272	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
19	30,428	Metazachlor	400	g/l				
20	30,429	Metazachlor	400	g/l				
21	30,430	Metazachlor	400	g/l				
22	30,733	Metazachlor	400	g/l	Řepka jarní			
23	30,733	Metazachlor	400	g/l	Zelenina - brukvovité			
24	30,733	Metazachlor	400	g/l	Řepka ošmá			
25	30,876	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
26	30,974	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
27	31,271	Metazachlor	375	g/l	Řepka jarní			
28	31,271	Metazachlor	375	g/l	Řepka ošmá			
29	31,271	Metazachlor	375	g/l	Řepka ošmá			
30	31,292	Metazachlor	375	g/l				
31	31,588	Metazachlor	500	g/l	Řepka ošmá			
32	31,619	Metazachlor	200	g/l				
33	31,620	Metazachlor	200	g/l				
34	31,621	Metazachlor	200	g/l				
35	31,622	Metazachlor	300	g/l				
36	31,636	Metazachlor	200	g/l				
37	31,661	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
38	32,600	Metazachlor	375	g/l	Řepka ošmá			
39	32,754	Metazachlor	500	g/l				
40	33,175	Metazachlor	250	g/l				
41	33,477	Metazachlor	300	g/l				
42	33,482	Metazachlor	214	g/l	Řepka ošmá	2,30	3,50	l/ha
43	33,484	Metazachlor	140	g/l				

Script 3: For the selected parameters above for metazachlor, display the count of entries per English name and crop type.

```

SELECT
--ppp.trade_name,
--ppp.id,
--deci.reg_number,

```



```
--deci.id,
--deci.package,
asu.name_en,
--asu.id,
--das.amount,
--das.unit,
sc.crops_type,
--sa.min_rate,
--sa.max_rate
count(*)
from
zb_stg_por.stg_decision deci
left join zb_stg_por.stg_ppp ppp on ppp.id = deci.id_ppp
left join zb_stg_por.stg_decision_as das on deci.id = das.dec_id
left join zb_stg_por.stg_active_subs asu on das.act_substance_id = asu.id
left join zb_stg_por.stg_use su on deci.id = su.decision_id
left join zb_stg_por.stg_use_crop suc on su.hash = suc.use_hash
left join zb_stg_por.stg_crop sc on suc.crops_hash = sc.hash
left join zb_stg_por.stg_application sa on sa.use_hash = su.hash

WHERE
name_en LIKE ('%Metazachlor%')
and deci.reg_number NOT LIKE ('%D%') AND deci.reg_number NOT LIKE ('%V%')
--and deci.package not like ('M') and deci.package not like ('V') ???
and (deci.dec_valid_till ::date BETWEEN '2020-01-01' AND '2020-12-31'
or deci.dec_valid_from ::date BETWEEN '2020-01-01' AND '2020-12-31'
or (deci.dec_valid_from ::date < '2020-01-01' AND deci.dec_valid_till ::date > '2020-12-31'))

group by
asu.name_en,
sc.crops_type
```

Outcome 3: the counts for metazachlor are displayed as requested.

a.s. name	Crop type	counts
Metazachlor	PL	58
Metazachlor	SK	1
Metazachlor		35

2.5.2 PPP use data

In the Czech Republic, also resolute data of individual a.s. use in each year for specific crop types are available. These can be retrieved in CSV or XLSX files for the whole country (see example in [Figure 2.3](#)) or even for each of 77 districts.

ACTIVE SUBSTANCE	BF	YEAR	TOTAL	CEREALS	MAIZE	LEGUMES	BEET	POTATOES	FORAGE CROPS	OIL PLANTS	HOPS	VEGETABLES	FRUITS	GRAPES	OTHERS
GLYPHOSATE	H	2020	489 534	259 347	48 573	5 859	9 546	3 462	15 688	85 136		2 013	7 093	8 189	24 627
CHLORMEQUAT	RR	2020	314 422	300 113						14 309					
TEBUCONAZOLE	F	2020	159 782	102 957	160					55 656		130	660	219	0
PETHOXAMID	H	2020	157 177		53 960					103 127			90		
METAZACHLOR	H	2020	131 923							131 099		769			54
SULPHUR	F	2020	127 295	2 611		148	394				2 671	940	37 367	83 145	20
CHLOROTOLURON	H	2020	112 684	108 130						4 554					
POTASSIUM HYDROGEN CARBON	F	2020	105 959								1 194		8 279	96 485	
MANCOZEB	F	2020	89 446					41 124		22 741		10 804	13 862	875	41
THIOPHANATE-METHYL	F	2020	86 414	31 945			11 879			42 590					
PENDIMETHALIN	H	2020	77 303	41 342	2 115	17 881			1 138	7 646		4 218	1 599	544	819
CHLORPYRIFOS	I	2020	73 435	9 436	82	316	262	43		63 296					
TERBUTHYLAZINE	H	2020	71 600	701	70 899										
SPIROXAMINE	F	2020	64 854	61 324										3 530	
PROCHLORAZ	F	2020	64 374	63 623			2			749					
METAMITRON	H	2020	61 141				60 924			4		212	1		
PROTHIOCONAZOLE	F	2020	60 189	45 911	449		1 622			12 205			2		
AZOXYSTROBIN	F	2020	53 105	23 701	44	517	2 501	1 345		56		852	1 031		56
DIMETHENAMID-P	H	2020	50 399		27 111		2 613			20 620				55	
S-METOLACHLOR	H	2020	50 195	1 169	48 010	124	308	104		481					
RAPESEED OIL METHYLESTER	AJ	2020	46 010	10 428	14 194	34	19 124	305	259	1 230		213	30		193
THIACLOPRID	I	2020	41 440	4 740	315	1 282	1 255	1 502	98	30 975		230	1 033		8
COPPER OXYCHLORIDE	F	2020	40 954					2 118			9 476	1 550	8 996	18 734	80
DIFLUFENICAN	H	2020	37 091	37 071						16					3
TRINEXAPAC-ETHYL	RR	2020	36 250	35 919						232		99			
PROSULFOCARB	H	2020	35 487	15 900				19 587							
FOLPET	F	2020	34 854								2 577			32 276	
FLUFENACET	H	2020	31 940	26 704	3 350			1 391		493					3
ETHEPHON	RR	2020	31 402	31 150									253		
2,4-D	H	2020	29 808	27 752	1 470								28		55
EPOXICONAZOLE	F	2020	28 660	26 320	139		2 200								
FOSETYL-AL	F	2020	27 582								8 919	1 053	737	16 837	37
MCPA	H	2020	26 785	24 315					2 452				18	1	
DI-1-P-MENTHENE	AJ	2020	25 494	7 214	918	706	426	265	534	12 976		115	642	1 641	58
PHENMEDIPHAM	H	2020	24 421				24 292					71	56		2
CAPTAN	F	2020	23 590										23 590		
FENPROPIIMORPH	F	2020	23 491	18 291			5 200								
DIFENOCONAZOLE	F	2020	23 064	7 880		3	2 873	2 921		8 132		309	603	342	1
BOSCALID (FORMERLY NICOBIFEN)	F	2020	21 924	4 453		113				13 708	1 562	294	881	912	
HEPTAMETHYLTRISILOXANE MOI	P	2020	20 552	10 851	1 066	132	600	771	81	4 741	59	539	590	1 035	86
PYRACLOSTROBIN	F	2020	19 820	16 903	458		1 205			6	794	74	333	48	
FLUROXYPYR	H	2020	19 519	16 110	757				229	2 423					
METCONAZOLE	F	2020	18 412	7 665						10 747					
QUINMERAC	H	2020	18 366				979			17 388					
ETHOFUMESATE	H	2020	18 156				18 140					14			2
FENPROPIDIN	F	2020	17 395	17 395											
RAPESEED OIL	AJ	2020	17 120	836	592	10	2 833	430	2	95		119	12 033		169
PALMITIC ACID, METHYL ESTER;	AJ	2020	16 751	8 735	957	1 419	150	27	1 541	3 916		5			
CHLOROTHALONIL	F	2020	16 462	14 515					38	1 909					
BENTAZONE	H	2020	16 449	3 197	454	4 925		111	5 324	2 438					

Figure 2.3. An example of the annual use data for the a.s. on several crop types for the Czech Republic in year 2020. Only the first 50 a.s. based on their total annual use are shown.

Table 2.2: Appraisal of the PPP registers retained in the 39 EU countries that were searched. Key to colour scale and weight assignments is explained under section on data availability among countries. High variability among different quality/relevance criteria, and across countries is observed.

nr	country	country code	Availability					Accessibility							Data resolution									
			online source/link	"search" option	institutional database	documentation /reporting	SCORE	contacts	database open at website	documents open at website	documents /data retrieved	easiness of resolute database retrieval	no payment requirement	instructions/ operation manual	English version	SCORE	active substance	formulated product	decision approval	application regime	crop	pest	SCORE	
1	Albania	AL																						
2	Austria	AT																						
3	Belarus	BY																						
4	Belgium	BE																						
5	Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA																						
6	Bulgaria	BG																						
7	Croatia	HR																						
8	Cyprus	CY																						
9	Czech Republic (Czechia)	CZ																						
10	Denmark	DK																						
11	Estonia	EE																						
12	Finland	FI																						
13	France	FR																						
14	Germany	DE																						
15	Greece (Hellas)	GR																						
16	Hungary	HU																						
17	Iceland	IS																						
18	Ireland	IE																						
19	Italy	IT																						
20	Latvia	LV																						
21	Lithuania	LT																						
22	Luxembourg	LU																						
23	Malta	MT																						
24	Moldova	MD																						
25	Montenegro	ME																						
26	Netherlands	NL																						
27	North Macedonia	MK																						
28	Norway	NO																						
29	Poland	PL																						
30	Portugal	PT																						
31	Romania	RO																						
32	Serbia	RS																						
33	Slovakia	SK																						
34	Slovenia	SI																						
35	Spain	ES																						
36	Sweden	SE																						
37	Switzerland	CH																						
38	Ukraine	UA																						
39	United Kingdom	UK																						

Table 2.2 – summary: The scores per criterion and the available document formats are displayed.

			Availability	Accessibility	Data resolution	
nr	country	country code	SCORE	SCORE	SCORE	document format
1	Albania	AL				
2	Austria	AT				excel
3	Belarus	BY				pdf
4	Belgium	BE				
5	Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA				
6	Bulgaria	BG				pdf
7	Croatia	HR				
8	Cyprus	CY				pdf
9	Czech Republic (Czechia)	CZ				excel
10	Denmark	DK				excel; pdf
11	Estonia	EE				pdf
12	Finland	FI				json
13	France	FR				csv, pdf
14	Germany	DE				pdf; excel
15	Greece (Hellas)	GR				pdf; excel
16	Hungary	HU				pdf
17	Iceland	IS				
18	Ireland	IE				pdf
19	Italy	IT				pdf; excel
20	Latvia	LV				html
21	Lithuania	LT				pdf
22	Luxembourg	LU				pdf
23	Malta	MT				excel
24	Moldova	MD				excel; pdf
25	Montenegro	ME				pdf
26	Netherlands	NL				excel
27	North Macedonia	MK				
28	Norway	NO				pdf
29	Poland	PL				excel; pdf
30	Portugal	PT				excel
31	Romania	RO				pdf
32	Serbia	RS				biannual print
33	Slovakia	SK				
34	Slovenia	SI				
35	Spain	ES				excel; pdf
36	Sweden	SE				pdf
37	Switzerland	CH				
38	Ukraine	UA				
39	United Kingdom	UK				

Table 2.3: The overview of the PPP registers retained in the 27 EU MSs

nr	country	country code	Availability					Accessibility										Data resolution						
			online source/link	"search" option	institutional database	documentation /reporting	SCORE	contacts	database open at website	documents open at website	documents /data retrieved	easiness of resolute database retrieval	no payment requirement	instructions/ operation manual	English version	SCORE	active substance	formulated product	decision approval	application regime	crop	pest	SCORE	
1	Austria	AT																						
2	Belgium	BE																						
3	Bulgaria	BG																						
4	Croatia	HR																						
5	Cyprus	CY																						
6	Czech Republic (Czechia)	CZ																						
7	Denmark	DK																						
8	Estonia	EE																						
9	Finland	FI																						
10	France	FR																						
11	Germany	DE																						
12	Greece (Hellas)	GR																						
13	Hungary	HU																						
14	Ireland	IE																						
15	Italy	IT																						
16	Latvia	LV																						
17	Lithuania	LT																						
18	Luxembourg	LU																						
19	Malta	MT																						
20	Netherlands	NL																						
21	Poland	PL																						
22	Portugal	PT																						
23	Romania	RO																						
24	Slovakia	SK																						
25	Slovenia	SI																						
26	Spain	ES																						
27	Sweden	SE																						

Table 2.4: Overview per different EU regulatory zone of formulated PPP authorizations: a) north, b) central, and c) southern

(a)

nr	country	country code	Availability					Accessibility							Data resolution								
			online source/link	"search" option	institutional database	documentation /reporting	SCORE	contacts	database open at website	documents open at website	documents /data retrieved	easiness of resolute database retrieval	no payment requirement	instructions/ operation manual	English version	SCORE	active substance	formulated product	decision approval	application regime	crop	pest	SCORE
1	Denmark	DK																					
2	Estonia	EE																					
3	Finland	FI																					
4	Latvia	LV																					
5	Lithuania	LT																					
6	Sweden	SE																					

(b)

nr	country	country code	Availability					Accessibility							Data resolution								
			online source/link	"search" option	institutional database	documentation /reporting	SCORE	contacts	database open at website	documents open at website	documents /data retrieved	easiness of resolute database retrieval	no payment requirement	instructions/ operation manual	English version	SCORE	active substance	formulated product	decision approval	application regime	crop	pest	SCORE
1	Austria	AT																					
2	Belgium	BE																					
3	Czech Republic (Czechia)	CZ																					
4	Germany	DE																					
5	Hungary	HU																					
6	Ireland	IE																					
7	Luxembourg	LU																					
8	Netherlands	NL																					
9	Poland	PL																					
10	Romania	RO																					
11	Slovakia	SK																					
12	Slovenia	SI																					

(c)

nr	country	country code	Availability					Accessibility							Data resolution								
			online source/link	"search" option	institutional database	documentation /reporting	SCORE	contacts	database open at website	documents open at website	documents /data retrieved	easiness of resolute database retrieval	no payment requirement	instructions/ operation manual	English version	SCORE	active substance	formulated product	decision approval	application regime	crop	pest	SCORE
1	Bulgaria	BG																					
2	Croatia	HR																					
3	Cyprus	CY																					
4	France	FR																					
5	Greece (Hellas)	GR																					
6	Italy	IT																					
7	Malta	MT																					
8	Portugal	PT																					
9	Spain	ES																					

Table 2.5- summary: The scores per criterion and the available document formats are displayed.

nr	country	country code	Availability	Accessibility	Data resolution	document format
1	Albania	AL				
2	Austria	AT				
3	Belarus	BY				
4	Belgium	BE				
5	Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA				
6	Bulgaria	BG				pdf
7	Croatia	HR				
8	Cyprus	CY				
9	Czech Republic (Czechia)	CZ				excel
10	Denmark	DK				pdf
11	Estonia	EE				many format options
12	Finland	FI				
13	France	FR				pdf; graphs interactive maps
14	Germany	DE				pdf
15	Greece (Hellas)	GR				
16	Hungary	HU				website
17	Iceland	IS				
18	Ireland	IE				pdf
19	Italy	IT				pdf
20	Latvia	LV				
21	Lithuania	LT				
22	Luxembourg	LU				pdf
23	Malta	MT				
24	Moldova	MD				
25	Montenegro	ME				
26	Netherlands	NL				many format options
27	North Macedonia	MK				
28	Norway	NO				csv; excel
29	Poland	PL				
30	Portugal	PT				pdf
31	Romania	RO				pdf
32	Serbia	RS				
33	Slovakia	SK				many formats
34	Slovenia	SI				many formats
35	Spain	ES				excel;pdf
36	Sweden	SE				pdf
37	Switzerland	CH				
38	Ukraine	UA				
39	United Kingdom	UK				csv

Table 2.6: The overview of the PPP uses data in the 27 EU MSs

nr	country	country code	Availability					Accessibility											Data resolution				
			online source/link	"search" option	institutional database	documentation/reporting	SCORE	contacts	database open at website	documents open at website	documents /data retrieved	easiness of resolute database retrieval	no payment requirement	instructions/ operation manual	English version	no confidentiality issues	SCORE	Frequency of data collection	Area		PPP amount		SCORE
																		local/ district specific	agricultural holding	actual PPP amount	active substance specific		
1	Austria	AT																					
2	Belgium	BE																					
3	Bulgaria	BG																					
4	Croatia	HR																					
5	Cyprus	CY																					
6	Czech Republic (Czechia)	CZ																					
7	Denmark	DK																					
8	Estonia	EE																					
9	Finland	FI																					
10	France	FR																					
11	Germany	DE																					
12	Greece (Hellas)	GR																					
13	Hungary	HU																					
14	Ireland	IE																					
15	Italy	IT																					
16	Latvia	LV																					
17	Lithuania	LT																					
18	Luxembourg	LU																					
19	Malta	MT																					
20	Netherlands	NL																					
21	Poland	PL																					
22	Portugal	PT																					
23	Romania	RO																					
24	Slovakia	SK																					
25	Slovenia	SI																					
26	Spain	ES																					
27	Sweden	SE																					

Table 2.7: Overview per different EU regulatory zone of formulated PPP authorizations: a) north, b) central, and c) southern

(a)

nr	country	country code	Availability				Accessibility										Data resolution								
			online source/link	"search" option	institutional database	documentation/reporting	SCORE	contacts	database open at website	documents open at website	documents /data retrieved	easiness of resolute database retrieval	no payment requirement	instructions/ operation manual	English version	no confidentiality issues	SCORE	Frequency of data collection	Area		PPP amount		SCORE		
																			local/ district specific	agricultural holding	actual PPP amount	active substance specific			
1	Denmark	DK																							
2	Estonia	EE																							
3	Finland	FI																							
4	Latvia	LV																							
5	Lithuania	LT																							
6	Sweden	SE																							

(b)

nr	country	country code	Availability				Accessibility										Data resolution									
			online source/link	"search" option	institutional database	documentation/reporting	SCORE	contacts	database open at website	documents open at website	documents /data retrieved	easiness of resolute database retrieval	no payment requirement	instructions/ operation manual	English version	no confidentiality issues	SCORE	Frequency of data collection	Area		PPP amount		SCORE			
																			local/ district specific	agricultural holding	actual PPP amount	active substance specific				
1	Austria	AT																								
2	Belgium	BE																								
3	Czech Republic (Czechia)	CZ																								
4	Germany	DE																								
5	Ireland	IE																								
6	Hungary	HU																								
7	Luxembourg	LU																								
8	Netherlands	NL																								
9	Poland	PL																								
10	Romania	RO																								
11	Slovakia	SK																								
12	Slovenia	SI																								

(c)

nr	country	country code	Availability				Accessibility										Data resolution										
			online source/link	"search" option	institutional database	documentation/reporting	SCORE	contacts	database open at website	documents open at website	documents /data retrieved	easiness of resolute database retrieval	no payment requirement	instructions/ operation manual	English version	no confidentiality issues	SCORE	Frequency of data collection	Area		PPP amount		SCORE				
																			local/ district specific	agricultural holding	actual PPP amount	active substance specific					
1	Bulgaria	BG																									
2	Croatia	HR																									
3	Cyprus	CY																									
4	France	FR																									
5	Greece (Hellas)	GR																									
6	Italy	IT																									
7	Malta	MT																									
8	Portugal	PT																									
9	Spain	ES																									

3 Usability of recently available European crop type map

In the SPRINT Toolbox, we aim to estimate environmental exposure to pesticides at national and European level for both humans and animals. For exposure assessment purposes, spatial data on crop type is fundamental. This data is used for exposure estimation and the minimum input consists of the type of crop (e.g., wheat) and crop location. In a next step, pesticide usage is assigned to a specific crop, which is then used in the exposure calculation steps.

In 2021, the first European crop type map was published (EU-Cropmap) (d'Andrimont et al. 2021)¹⁵. This map is based on Sentinel-1 data and LUCAS Copernicus in-situ observations. The published map (**Figure 3.1**) has a 10x10-m spatial resolution and pertains to the year 2018. Before using the crop data presented in this map as input to the modelling chain (developed in WP3), we investigated 1) How accurate is the map for the corresponding year (i.e., 2018) and 2) If the map could also be used to represent (with some error) other years.

Figure 3.1. EU crop type map for 2018 (the map covers the then 28 countries of the European Union and thus not Norway, Switzerland, and some Balkan states). [Reprinted from d'Andrimont et al. 2021]

¹⁵ d'Andrimont, R., Verhegghen, A., Lemoine, G., Kempeneers, P., Meroni, M., & van der Velde, M. (2021). From parcel to continental scale – A first European crop type map based on Sentinel-1 and LUCAS Copernicus in-situ observations. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 266, 112708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112708>

To assess the usability of the afore mentioned map for exposure assessment, we compared several major crops from the EU-Cropmap with the crops reported by farmers in the Netherlands (BRP_Gewaspercelen) for the years 2018 and 2019 (accessible via PDOK WFS 2022). The Dutch data are based on high-resolution cadastral data of parcels, in addition to farmers' reports of the crop they grew on the specific parcel. As such, the Dutch data are a useful reference to compare the European crop data set with another data set with likely higher precision (spatially and regarding crop type).

The comparison was done by first, selecting 5000 random addresses in the Netherlands and second, calculating the area of each crop inside 100, 250, 500, and 1000 meters buffer zone around the selected addresses based on the European map as well as in the Dutch maps. The comparison uses the underlying assumption that area of a crop corresponds to amount of a specific pesticide used in the vicinity of homes. Spearman correlation was used to assess agreement between areas of the same crop. The results are shown in **Table 3.1** for the comparison between EU-Cropmap vs BRP_Gewaspercelen for 2018 and 2019.

Table 3.1. Spearman correlations for some major crop areas between EU-Cropmap vs BRP_Gewaspercelen for 2018 and 2019

Crop	Buffer meters 100		Buffer meters 250		Buffer meters 500		Buffer meters 1000	
	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019
Barley	0.61	-0.18	0.84	0.17	0.69	0.31	0.63	0.39
Corn	0.80	0.51	0.78	0.55	0.66	0.56	0.53	0.47
Wheat	0.84	0.01	0.88	0.29	0.89	0.47	0.92	0.77
Potatoes	0.78	0.12	0.71	0.16	0.67	0.29	0.55	0.41
Tulip, flower bulbs and tubers	nd	0.19	0.21	0.06	0.61	0.12	0.60	0.44
Grassland	0.75	0.76	0.78	0.82	0.78	0.86	0.69	0.86
Sugar beet	0.76	0.02	0.81	0.28	0.75	0.33	0.77	0.17

Overall, correlations were moderate to strong for most crops for the 2018 comparison, indicating that satellite-derived maps for Europe may be a good approximation for actual crop type maps. This result was anticipated as the map was developed based on measurements from 2018 and the map evaluation was also performed for 2018. However, when comparing with 2019 crops, correlations were overall low, with the exception for corn and grassland, as well as wheat for the buffer of 1000 meters. Therefore, the published EU-Cropmap is not likely to produce accurate environmental pesticide exposure results when using other years, except for 2018. This is until further years become accessible.

4 Dietary exposure assessment in European countries

Dietary intake is one of the major routes of human exposure to pesticides¹⁶. The goal of this work is to calculate average human dietary exposure to plant protection products (PPP) in European countries. In this exercise, we aim to produce dietary intake calculations at the EU country level and subsequently generate exposure maps.

For exposure assessment, two main data sets were used: **data on PPP residue in food items** and **data on food consumption** in European countries.

For **pesticide residues**, results of national control activities carried out by the EU Member States, Iceland and Norway were utilized which are available as an open-access source on the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) web¹⁷. Such data are obligatory collected by the EU Member States based on Regulation (EC) 396/2005 in the controls ensuring that food placed on the market is compliant with the legal limits. According to Article 31 of this Regulation, Member States are requested to share the results of the official controls and other relevant information with the European Commission, EFSA and other Member States. The raw data provided by reporting countries and anonymized by EFSA can also be downloaded from the Open Science platform Zenodo¹⁸ by typing: "*Member-State-Name* results from the monitoring of pesticide residues in food". Data are reported annually by every country and include the results of all individual analyses of a variety of PPP on a diverse set of food items. We assume that all national data on PPP residues in food are made available in Zenodo and in EFSA reports, because when each country has become part of the EU controlling program, it is obliged to send the analysed data to EFSA and then EFSA publishes them online. A summary of the availability of data for participating countries is presented in **Table 4.1**. According to this table, the availability of the data is quite noticeable and except for Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, and North Macedonia, for other countries reported data covers all the time range. The raw PPP data from all the countries (originally as CSV files with thousands of rows, having a unified coding system) were merged using R programming. Accordingly, new datasets were obtained representing the PPP residues in the analysed food items in all participating countries for each year from 2011 to 2020. From these new datasets, the result for desired individual active substances (a.s.) can be easily filtered.

For the food consumption data, EFSA source¹⁹ was explored. However, the drawback of this database is that the items does not always match the food items regularly analysed for pesticides. Hence, the data for food consumption was taken from the Raw Primary Commodity (RPC) model²⁰ which has utilized the EFSA Comprehensive Database as the input, containing 51 dietary surveys from 23 different countries, to derive RPC consumption data and has developed a new Consumption Database accordingly. In this data, the consumption (g/day) of every food item (mean, median, 75th, 90th, 95th, 97.5th, and 99th

¹⁶ Lu C. et al. 2006. Organic diets significantly lower children's dietary exposure to organophosphorus pesticides. *Environ Health Perspect* 114: 260–263. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.8418>; Rempelos et al. 2022. Diet and food type affect urinary pesticide residue excretion profiles in healthy individuals: results of a randomized controlled dietary intervention trial. *Am J Clin Nutr* 115: 364–377. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/ngab308>

¹⁷ [https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/toc/10.1002/\(ISSN\)1831-4732.CHEMICALRESIDUES-DATA#heading-level-1-2](https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/toc/10.1002/(ISSN)1831-4732.CHEMICALRESIDUES-DATA#heading-level-1-2)

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/food-consumption-data>

²⁰ Dujardin & Kirwan. 2019. The raw primary commodity (RPC) model: strengthening EFSA's capacity to assess dietary exposure at different levels of the food chain, from raw primary commodities to foods as consumed. *EFSA Support Publ* 16. <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1532>

percentiles) has been reported separately for each country. The consumption data will be connected to the PPP residues data sets for the dietary exposure calculations.

In the first step, and to use the data for specific PPP residues on foodstuff, the data related to each a.s. reported in every single reporting year by all the participating countries were merged. Next, five food items with a higher number of available reports and a lower number of values below the limit of quantification (LOQ) were selected ($x-x\% < \text{LOQ}$) for further processing. We applied imputation (using maximum likelihood estimation regression) to estimate likely average PPP residues, taking the distribution of the values, the LOQ and the number of samples into account. We provide here an example map of boscalid residue on strawberries for the year 2011 ([Figure 4.1](#)).

Table 4.1: Availability of raw data on the PPP residues in the national food controlling programs released by EFSA.

Country of origin	Year of report										Data format
	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	
Austria	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Belgium	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Bosnia and Herzegovina	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Bulgaria	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Croatia	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Cyprus	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Czech Republic	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Denmark	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Estonia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Finland	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
France	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Germany	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Greece	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Hungary	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Iceland	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Ireland	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Italy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Latvia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Lithuania	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Luxembourg	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Malta	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Montenegro	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Netherlands	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
North Macedonia	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Norway	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Poland	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Portugal	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Romania	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Slovakia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Slovenia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Spain	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
Sweden	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV
United Kingdom	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	CSV

"✓": Available
 "-": Not available

Figure 4.1: Example of boscalid residues in strawberries in 2011 for countries for which PPP data on food items are available in the EFSA database. Longitude and latitude data for each country was provided by the ggplot2 package (accessible via `map_data("world")`). Data for grey regions were not available.

5 European maps of PPP emissions and environmental concentrations

We aim to include estimates of PPP environmental concentrations at European level in the SPRINT-toolbox, based on results from the multiscale, multimedia PANGEA model²¹. A preliminary step for this is to enhance the representation of PPP transport processes inside the model. We approach this by integrating in PANGEA spatially-distributed estimates for Europe of surface runoff and soil erosion, recently computed with the PESERA model under the SoilCare project²².

PESERA calculates monthly values for runoff and soil erosion for Europe with a 500 m resolution, from 1981 to 2010; an example of the results is shown in **Figure 5.1**. The integration of this work in PANGEA requires post-processing of the results to conform with the model's data requirements. The work done so far for WP5 consisted of meetings between model developers and users from both sides, to discuss the processes and assumptions in terms of spatial and temporal scales, and how they can be integrated.

From this work, we established a protocol to convert PESERA outputs into PANGEA inputs, which will require a spatial integration using PANGEA's river basin structure, a temporal integration towards long-term averages, and the calculation of erosion in volume instead of mass. We are currently implementing this protocol so that we can test how PANGEA performs when using these updated inputs.

Figure 5.1: simulated long-term average erosion rates across Europe using the PESERA model.

²¹ Wannaz et al. 2018. Multiscale Spatial Modeling of Human Exposure from Local Sources to Global Intake. *Environmental Science & Technology* 52: 701-711. DOI: 10.1021/acs.est.7b05099

²² Baartman et al. 2022. The effects of Soil Improving Cropping Systems (SICS) on soil erosion and SOC stocks across Europe: a simulation study. *Land* 11: 943. DOI: 10.3390/land11060943

6 Conclusions

PPP data (national PPP registers) and PPP usage (national statistics on pesticides) are the most challenging data to collect and harmonize. So far, we have done an overview of these data in all European countries and described their parameters (metadata). For two data reach countries (the Netherlands and the Czech Republic), we have explored in detail the structure and properties of these data and the same is started for the selected countries from the northern and southern zone. For the Czech annual PPP use data, we have mined the a.s.-specific and crop-specific consumption in all districts and hold it currently in Excel (will be imported to SQL database). The Czech PPP register was considered as a reference model, and we have translated it to the data warehouse enabling flexible data mining by SQL scripts.

The compilation of the Czech database was achieved through long term (over one year), systematic and continuous contacts with the Czech authorities on data-structure reorganization, clarifications on methods of data collection or estimates, provision of information not available online, and unfolding data aggregation into comprehensive datasets. **Generalized most probable steps needed** to follow in each country considering the difficulties and time constraints expected, based on the experience with the Czech dataset are:

- A common harmonized platform with sources to PPP registers and use
- More resolute data related to PPP application regimes, crops and pests targeted, available for each PPP in a format that allows for easier data mining and analysis.
- Common methodology and terminology in data mining and estimations
- English version available
- Clarification of the precision and frequency needed for data collection and updates (a more coordinated and systematic scheme is necessary for comparability across countries)
- To overcome confidentiality issues

With regard to the **crop maps**, we confirmed that satellite-derived maps for Europe may be a good approximation for actual crop type maps.

With regard the **dietary exposure**, we have compiled the data on PPP residues in food and explored the possible way for food consumption patterns estimations. The pilot calculation for boscalid in strawberries shows that assigning PPP residue levels to food stuffs is possible, at least for food items with a sufficiently high number of samples and residue levels above the LOQ. In a next step we will calculate residue levels for Europe for a larger set of food items across several years. We will subsequently assign residue levels (on a European level) to food intake (on national level) to derive European maps of likely PPP dietary intake.

Apparently, it is challenging to compile all the data needed as explained in the previous chapters. However, after this work is done, the tools will pose very high predictive value with regard the PPP strategies and decisions. The overall idea of the Tool III.B is illustrated in **Figure 6.1**.

